

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE LED NOTICE BOARD BY USING ZIGBEE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

By taking care of the today's world it is more essential to make our self run with it's time, so that our work is accomplished within some second of time and it is becomes possible by technology. LED notice board is one of the great application of this type of the technology. In this we were introducing wireless technology by make the used of two zigbee module which is present at the transmitter side and the receiver side arduino based AT mega 328 is used as microcontroller for no package loss in term of the words. So this is all about the design of our proposed system. We are making the use of red LED for lightning so if it is replace by the RGB then it will comes under the future scenario, this is the big and primary point. The proposed system is water proof and transmission of the massages is done by using the LED MAGIC software which is costume made and not even available on the open source level so this is one of the limitation of our system.

Keyword:- zigbee module, arduino, AT mega 328, LED notice board, LED MAGIC .

I. INTRODUCTION

As wireless technology is introduced in the world everything is just mobile. So we can say it as so helpful because it refuses the effort of servicing the thing without moving a inch. With the wireless technology, the embedded C is also the useful interfacing language as it is composed of data structured c language as well as embedded language. Hence it is good to those people who are working for new invention in microcontroller.

The whole system "notice board" is working under the basic principle of transmitting and receiving the message. As it is primary thing which is happening under the wireless technology.

The concept is simple; the master computer is one who is only responsible to access the system. The slaves are its follower and the master complete is the main prior as it has all its rights reserved.

We are going to plan the login system in main master computer. So that the user can access the system simply by loading passwords and ID. Hence, nobody can make the misuse of system.

If the slave computer have to transfer or wants to share anything on the notice board then first it will

Share the message with master pc and the user or the master pc can take the decision whether it is displayable on the notice board or not.

The MAX 232 is used in system for the serial communication in between the pc and notice board.

Table represents various zigbee modules on the basis of performance parameters-

Vendor	Module Name	Bandwidth	Max. data rate	Line of sight range
Texas Instruments	CC2520	2.4GHz	128 Kb to 256 Kb	400 m to 500 m
Free scale	MC1323x	2.4GHz	128 Kb	300 m
NXP	JN516x	2.4GHz	64 Kb to 256 Kb	30 m to 100 m
Atmel	ATZB24BO	2.4GHz	128 Kb	6 km

Table represents various microcontroller used in LED notice board.

Trademark	Code of Microcontroller	Flash Memory	Pin Count.	Operating Current	Operating Voltage
AVR	AT mega 328	32 Kb	28	40 mA	1.8V to 5.5V
AVR	AT89c51	4 Kb	40	15 mA	6.6 V
AVR	AT89C52	8 Kb	40	15 mA	6.6 V
Microchip	PIC16F877A	8 Kb	28	25 mA	2 V to 5.5 V

II. BASIC WORKING

As the master pc can send the command on the notice board. And it happens only with the help of the LED magic software. With the help of LED magic software, we can adjust the fonts, size, languages and brightness of LED's too. It is also capable of giving timing delay to the LED glowing.

Zigbee or the transmitter side is only capable of sending the information to the LED notice board which is at the receiver side. At the receiver side there will be another zigbee installed which will accept the command from the transmitter and will pass it to through the microcontroller and it will be displayed on the notice board. So whatever the command is showing on the notice board is keep scrolling until the new command is not send to the receiver. The various types of the animations are also adjustable on the notice board. So this is the basic principal of working.

III. HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

1) Microcontroller (AT mega 328)

Microcontroller is used for interfacing the LED display with pc to display message. AT 89c52 is low power, high performance CMOS 8 bit microcontroller with 8 kb of flash program and erasable read only memory. But

here in our system, we are using the latest version of microcontroller i.e. AT mega 328 to achieve the aim as it have some specialization as follows.

- Advance RISC architecture
- 131 powerful instruction executed in one clock cycle.
- 32 kb self program, flash program memory.
- 23 program i/o line.
- 28 pin PDIP.

2) Zigbee module (CC2520)

Here in our system we using the two zigbee modules under the name of trans receiver one is installed at transmitter side and other is installed at receiver side. It has some specialization as follows.

- 400 m line of sight range.
- Temperature range is (-40 degree C to +125 degree C)
- Operated up to 125 degree C and low voltage operator.
- CC2520 provides extensive hardware supports for frame handling, data buffering, bus transmission,

Sorting of zigbee

i) Zigbee coordinator (Zc):-

More comfort thing which is able to make way to transmission tree which connect other transmission network. It stores data about network consisting acts as a trust centre.

ii) Zigbee router (Zr):-

As well as running an application function, a router can act as an intermediate router passing a data for other device which transform data from one device to other.

iii) Zigbee end device (zed):-

In this kind of zigbee communication can be done with the help of the router. If it cannot relay the signal from other device.

Fig 1 shows zigbee networks

Fig 2 shows connection of zigbee devices

3) LED matrix board or display unit

LED notice board is made up of simple red led and RGB led i.e. red, green, blue here in our system we use the red led as it is even chipper then the RGB led. The decade counter IC, shift register IC, EPROM IC, etc. The LED notice board is arranged into in the form of 5 by 1 as it becomes more convenient to display the message on the notice board. The high intensity led light is used here as it is not harm the naked eyes anymore and it feels good to the eyes. Improper color reproduction, spreading of the light, and dimming problem, are avoided here.

Fig. 3 shows LED notice board

4) Power supply

The power supply is one of the most important factor and part of the circuit as it provides required supply to different block of circuit input 230v AC. The main block include transformer, rectifier circuit, filter circuit and regulated circuit.

Fig.4 circuit diagram of power supply

IV. SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

1) Proteus

It is the best ever simulation software for different arrangement with microcontroller and it is most famous as any. Due to availability of almost all microcontroller in it so it so sophisticated handy thinks to text program and embedded design for electronics hobbyist. We can arrange the program of the microcontroller in the proteus simulation software. After the simulating the circuit in the proteus software we can directly make the PCB design with it, so it should be the complete pack of performance for the learner.

2) Embedded C

Embedded C is the set of language extension for the C program language. Here in this system there is need to burn the operative microcontroller for queck response of any commands or task so for that there is need to do the programming for that and this programming is done in Embedded C.

Embedded C is highly implementive microcontroller programmable language and nowadays almost all engineers are doing there carries in one of the most useble language of recent era and i.e embedded c.

There is a large and growing international demand for programmers with 'embedded' skills, and many desktop developers are starting to move into this important area. Because most embedded projects have severe cost constraints.

Advantages

- It is small and easy to implement, understanding, and easy to debugging.
- It is most efficient.

3) LED magic

LED MAGIC most important software need to run the given system. This software is composed by .NET language. LED MAGIC consists of all options with library to control notice board wirelessly. LED MAGIC software stored in master computers and from where the HOD or highbred authority must send commands, Access various fonts, adjusts the sequence, adjust the delay and many more. LED MAGIC software is also called as image processing software.

Fig. 5 shows View of LED MAGIC software

V. APPLICATION

- **College**

Displaying students related notice just like placement news, guest information, time table, welcome news.

- **Railway station**

To indicates the perfect timing about arrival and departure of the trains.

- **Share market**

LED notice board is used their as it indicates latest updates of the share so that it is good for the broadcasting.

- **Restaurants**

To displays the menu as well as the various offers

VI. BLOCK DIAGRAM

1) TRANSMITTER SIDE

Fig.6 shows block diagram of transmitter

The block diagram of transmitter is shown above. At mega 328 is used because the data storing capacity is very large as compared to at mega 16. The capacity is 32 byte. Zigbee is used to transmit the data from microcontroller to display board. Pin 2 and 3 is transmitter and receiver pin. Again some data is coming from pc to microcontroller. Port d is an 8 bit bidirectional I/O port with internal pull up resistor port d output buffer have symmetrical drive characteristics with both high sink and source capability. As input port d which is externally pulled low source current if pull up resistors are activated. The port d pin are tri stated when a reset condition

become active, even if the clock is not running, pc data is in image form which is directly fed on display board due to that the capacity requirement of microcontroller is very high. +5v power supply is used to drive the microcontroller circuit.

Fig.6 shows over view and down view of zigbee model at transmitter side

2) RECEIVER SIDE:-

Fig.7 block diagram of receiver

Now the signal will enter into the receiving portion after transmitting from the transmitter, receiver side consist of zigbee module at the starting of the notice board as it is indicated already in block diagram. After that zigbee will sends signal to microcontroller. Microcontroller will gives respond to the signal which is transmitted by zigbee to microcontroller, now microcontroller decode the commands and send it reliably to the next step. Our next step is display board where the commands are display after the whole process. After passed commands from microcontroller to notice board the components inside the notice board gate accessed to performed task glow the LEDs. Hence in such way system starts running. Zigbee is used to receive the data from microcontroller and send to display board pin 2 and 3 is transmitter and receiver pin. Display board is in matrix form which displays the data in image form using row and column. Pc data is in image form which is directly fed on display board due to that the capacity requirement of microcontroller is very high. + 5v power supply is used to drive the microcontroller circuit and 3.2 v supply for zigbee module. Data transmission capacity of zigbee is 2.4 GHz and display board requires 12v, 3A current.

VII. SYSTEM DESIGN:-

The proposed system consists of transmission section and receiver section. The circuit diagram is given below.

Fig. 8 schematic

VIII. FUTURE SCENARIO

The modes are capable to display the message in the two lines at the same time message in the two lines at the same line.

Robot is also a way to sends the commands.

The system is also run on the GSM as well as WIFI technology.

IX. CONCLUSION

Just only due to the wireless technology we able to communicate more efficient and fastly and with high efficiency we able to display the message i.e. without wasting the time we aim a things it also having the low maintenance and errors. So y taking the above information in mind the same system is planted on the railway station, bus stops, hotels, restaurants, share markets and so on, so that the extra attention of crowd becomes less. It is the cost efficient system and very easy to handle. The commanding host is only the prescribed person so that it provides personal authentication hence nobody from the outside make the miss use of the system.

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